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THE INEXPRESSIBLE DAO-WAY OF ČIURLIONIS: REFLECTIONS OF DISTANT WORLDS IN THE SONATA PAINTINGS

Video of presentation: <https://youtu.be/ahYVNPgqYw>

The paper explores concepts of 氣 qi and 道 Dao to engage in the works of M. K. Čiurlionis. This perspective helps to rediscover Čiurlionis, and at the same time, Čiurlionis helps to understand and explain these seemingly abstract concepts. The concepts of qi and Dao are inseparable from Chinese aesthetics. The inexhaustibility of both of them reveals the dimension which awakens the viewer to a lively movement, freeing them from the limitations of the world of “sleeping” objects. Therefore, the concepts of qi and Dao enable us to speak about Čiurlionis’ work in a completely new way, using ideas that have not yet been developed in Western aesthetics. The paper explores the intercultural dialogue’s dimension that provides new keys to comparative aesthetics.

Keywords: M. K. Čiurlionis, 氣 qi, 道 Dao, comparative aesthetics, intercultural dialogue, inexpressibility, being and non-being.

There are two kinds of knowledge: the knowledge expressed in words, and the exact knowledge understood by the spirit but not expressed in words. Words cannot even begin to explain how such understanding arises; all we can say is that it is truly wondrous.

It would be foolish and crude to try to transmit the Light of Knowledge in unrefined language.

It would be as ludicrous as resorting to absurd conventional terms.

1925. Leaves of Morya’s Garden

It seems to me that these two quotes from the Leaves of Morya’s Garden “Illumination” are particularly appropriate to begin my discourse on Čiurlionis’ Dao-Path – as it unfolds in the *Spring Sonata*. The title of my presentation is “The Ineffable Dao-Path of Čiurlionis: Reflections of Far Away Worlds in the Works of the *Sonata Series*.”

With this discourse, I will continue the path that my Chinese colleagues and I have started – exploring Čiurlionis’ Asian and Chinese positions. I am very interested in Chinese thought and Chinese philosophy, and I think many of the ideas are very practical and have a life application. And to my surprise, quite recently, I discovered that perhaps some ideas can be much easier understood through art – through art performed by masters such as Čiurlionis. I therefore believe that, with this discourse, I am engaging in intercultural dialogue. I use the concepts of 氣 *qi* and 道 *Dao*, like some new keys, a perspective that helps me to rediscover our Čiurlionis, and at the same time Čiurlionis helps me to understand and explain these sometimes seemingly abstract concepts. There are two types of knowledge: expressed in words and inexpressible. It can be understood that these two types of knowledge correspond to two worlds.

I divided my account into six parts. I have named the first part “gates” and there I will briefly mention *Dao* and how *Dao* can help to delve into art, and in this case, into Čiurlionis. Later I will continue discussing the individual paintings and will end my discourse with some conclusions.

What is *Dao*? Probably many of us have already heard and know about it, but in the context of Čiurlionis, I want to draw attention to a few interesting features of *Dao*, which are very useful in aesthetic research.

First, I would like to point out the following basic meanings of *Dao* related to the character of *Dao*, and its etymological origin. In the most basic sense *Dao* is a path, and I wonder how often we see images of a path in Čiurlionis’ paintings, for instance even in this painting called *Fairy Tale*. It is not just a physical concrete path, but primarily a spiritual or inner path. The path of improvement we go through in our lives.

The second Lithuanian word that is very close to the word *Dao* is the word truth. Not just a logical physical truth, but truth that is spiritual, truth that reflects the cosmos, truth from which the universe begins and by which it is guided. This is also the truth as the Absolute, depicted in Čiurlionis’ paintings as *Rex*.

In addition to these two basic meanings of *Dao*, I want to point out three qualities that are commonly used to describe *Dao*. The first and foremost aspect of *Dao*, especially if we delve into the Daoist tradition of Laozi, is that

Dao is ineffable. And again, one could go deeper, go into metaphysics asking what ineffable means, but if we approach this question simply, we will see that there are many things in life that we cannot usually express in words. You can especially see that in art, like in this Čiurlionis painting called *Silence*, we can say so little about it, compared to what we feel and experience while appreciating the painting. We understand that what we feel, and experience cannot be easily expressed in words, thus is ineffable.

Another feature of *Dao* is a certain dialectic – *Dao* is described in Chinese terms 有 *you* and 無 *wu*. Generally speaking, *one* is all that *is* and *wu* is all that *is not*. These terms can also be understood as being and non-being, as expressed and unexpressed, but again, if we study the paintings, we will usually see that Čiurlionis' paintings, like those of Eastern tradition, contain a very important idea – the significance of paying attention not only to what is, but also to what seems to be absent. For example, in this painting the elements that are present are evident, they have a shape and form, they are filled with content. But the light that comes from above is like a blank sheet, like a space, it is what is not there. Exactly this play, the boundary between what is and what is not – is constantly altered, and fascinatedly functions in Čiurlionis' paintings, especially in his mature works.

The third quality of *Dao* is what I call the subtle. One of the subtlest manifestations of *Dao* is *qi* or psychic energy. And again, it is very difficult to find the most suitable translation of *qi-energy*, but *qi* can be associated and understood as a kind of spiritual fire, as light, as energy, as a play of colors. Color is also a manifestation of *qi* as well as a type of fire and light. And even more interesting is that we can understand *qi* as thoughts and feelings. When talking about a human being, *qi* implies concentrated thought. Thought is understood as a living organism filled with *qi*. For example, as in this Čiurlionis painting *Thought*, we see that thought is spatial, huge, and not just a chemical activity in the brain.

Thus, these two basic meanings of *Dao* and the three qualities can be used as a certain method or a key to delve into Čiurlionis' work. To simplify, I formulate these three qualities and two meanings of *Dao* as simple questions. That is, every time we look at Čiurlionis' pictures we can ask what is the very first feeling of *qi*? Just like when meeting a person for the first time, what feeling, what energy does a person feel when looking at a particular picture?

Next, to delve into the picture in the *Dao* sense, it is important to pay attention not only to what is obviously depicted in the picture, but also to what is not there, or what is only hinted there, what is perhaps outside of the painting. It also evokes the fact that we can ask not only what is expressed in a picture, but what is not expressed. Again, can we also ask what is the living truth that is reflected in the picture? How do we personally experience and feel that truth? And finally, we can usually just ask where the path is leading, where it is going, where it is coming from and where it is going to, in a particular painting or in a whole set of a sonata.

Let's start with the first painting *Allegro* from *Sonata of the Spring*, which I for the sake of convenience call "Flowers". As with every painting, we first look by stopping our thought, by stopping our gaze, and just meditating, looking at the picture and trying to feel what that very first sense of *qi* is like. And what's interesting, if we all look at this picture together now, almost everyone will feel a certain impulse, a certain feeling that emanates from the painting as a certain *qi-energy*. But we are often untrained to catch that feeling, we miss it, it passes like lightning, like a whiff, almost unnoticed. Even more, it is hard to catch those non-verbal feelings, even when they are noticed, because they were not shaped with words they are easily forgotten. But the idea of *qi* implies that we can calm ourselves down, reach tranquility, and gaze at the painting, observing how it reveals itself through *qi-energy*.

First, these willow seedlings, which seem to be barely recovering after winter, stand out. But if we observe the flow of *qi-energy*, the first feeling is that the energy is coming from above, in the form of a spiral and a Z-shaped trajectory traveling through the image, and eventually at the bottom it seems to turn into a river. The impression is that everything is a certain flow, and what is interesting is that the direction of that flow is not only from the top down, but going from the bottom, it seems to be a meandering river that passes through several realms and flows upwards. Again, according to *Dao* and *qi*, all this feeling of energy is something inexpressible, something that is not in the picture. However, this energy plays a very important role here.

There are so many elements in each picture that can be discussed and watched separately, but in my discourse, I will try to draw attention only to certain fundamental, perhaps more interesting or important moments.

Interestingly, looking at this picture for a long time, at first rationally, it is very difficult to say what is depicted here, what these trees mean, what those water bodies mean. Initially it seems that the water bodies are just some reflections and then later they start to appear like empty holes. Looking at the picture further, I was surprised and amazed that after a long observation I saw that this element is mysterious – is it a flower, a blade of grass, or does it resemble something like those willow seedlings? When looking even further, however, suddenly you come to the realization that a certain mythical creature is depicted here. And the further you look, the more convincing it looks. Here is the mouth, here are the teeth. The question arises as to what the truth of this picture is, what this mythical being means. Is it a sign of good or evil? It is reminiscent of the *Serpent Sonata*. Perhaps it is the winter that ends and takes off, and that gives its strength to the emergence of a new being.

We move on to the next picture *Andante*. *Andante* in musical terms implies a slightly slower rhythm, unlike the previous painting *Allegro*. The *Andante* painting, which can also be called the “windmill” or “windmills” when viewed with that *qi* gaze, first catches the eye with this world or this sphere. It seems as if the whole picture is divided into three parts, into three worlds, or realms of being.

First comes the closest, I would say earthly realm. Looking at the earthly realm, it seems to come to life, and especially for Lithuanians reminds them of the most beautiful places in Lithuania. An image of Kernavė, followed by the images of the grove in Punia. The grove of Punia is surrounded by a bend of the river Nemunas. Vivid images of Druskininkai also come to mind. We become encompassed by certain pleasant feelings that seem to take us back to those beautiful moments in the past when we were in those amazing places in nature.

Looking further, however, we note that upwards is another realm, another world, which in theosophical terminology we might perhaps call a stellar or astral world, or a subtle world. Subtle World. There is an impressive windmill here which can often symbolize a certain spiritual powerhouse, as well as man. A spiritual powerhouse in the sense that man can go through life, walk the path of life, accepting various light, dark, good and bad experiences, joys and failures, transforming them through his spiritual powerhouse and turning them into some spiritual nourishment.

It will soon be easy to see that in the center of the mill is the figure of a certain man-sage, standing calmly and quietly. The windmill also stands as a symbol of a man, of a man understood as spiritual alchemist.

Moving on further above, you see that there is a third, let's say heavenly realm. And interestingly, these different realms are like reflections of each other. According to the law of Hermes Trismegist, as above so is below. Each windmill has its own counterpart in different realms. In the foreground we see six mills, which could also be people who have reached certain heights, as they are on mounds – symbols of the accumulations of life's wisdom.

We see in the background six or even seven mills, one of which is hidden. Further above are four mills. Those four mills above are reflected in the yellow-gold mills. Upon further observation, we also see that in addition to this main windmill, there is a windmill whose center is beyond the picture. Here is a picture of a wing of the windmill, there is another wing of the same windmill, then another, so it seems that the center of the windmill is somewhere right there above the top, and while center creates the impression of a light source or sun.

Going back to the five keys I mentioned, this windmill, which is not in the painting, is one of the best examples of that inexpressible or idea that something is not. Even looking longer, we see that where the mill ends, it continues as far as certain rays, right here, and when we continue observing, we see that these elements here are also like the rays of a wing of a huge windmill. Finally, there seems to be a third giant windmill somewhere in space, somewhere beyond the painting.

We move on to the third painting of this *Sonata – Scherzo*. In the musical sense it implies comparison or repetition, which I will talk about later. Returning to our five keys, we look at the picture by directing our gaze and thoughts as still as possible. As we calm ourselves down, we listen to what the first sense of *qi* is, and how we see the flow of *qi* in this painting. If in the "Windmill" painting that flow comes out of the picture toward us or into the picture from us. Then here again, in this sense of *qi*, the *qi* S-shaped path seems to repeat itself. It begins in the high celestial spheres, goes down diagonally from the top, and finally takes a certain bend.

In this picture, the first thing that catches your eye is the huge fish, calm, free, at the bottom of the sea, accompanied by two other fish. We see three groups of fish, with three fish in each group, and the biggest riddle here – what’s the meaning, the truth of this fish net, perhaps a cosmic net. And why is it so resonating with the image of a mythical creature in the first painting of *Allegro*? If in the second painting the windmill plays a central role, then here is this cosmic web. Whether this web means shackles and calamity, or whether it is a web symbolizing joy, meaning that a fisherman or a person going through life has caught a certain catch, and returns happy that he is not empty-handed.

Again, from the fish perspective, maybe some of them are caught in this net, and the three closer ones are the ones that managed to break free, or not get caught in the net of life.

You can also see that behind the fish net, deep on the seabed, there are some contours of towers or a civilization. Is it an allusion to the Atlantis? Maybe it is also related to the legend of Jūratė and Kastytis?

It is in this painting that the musical play, with the pictures that went before, arises. In this painting there is a fish motif – three fish on the left, three on the right, but returning to the windmill painting, these fish are depicted as three clouds. Three clouds on the left, three on the right. If you come back earlier, there are no more fish, no more clouds, but there are these mysterious bodies of water or lakes. Four above, three below, and four more at the bottom. These paintings seem to be playing with each other and with these symbols, which turn from one thing, from one symbol into another. Also, there is a very interesting play with the main theme, the main line that I tried to draw earlier. That line flows like this. Even in the windmill, it can be seen as a spiral turn, and also as the flow of S-shaped *qi*; similarly in the fish painting.

The paintings play with each other – in one place three lakes, three clouds, three fish, three worlds, three buoys. Each picture can serve as a key to understanding the next picture. The windmill is particularly striking with those three distinct realms. Incidentally, if the river Nemunas is at the bottom, then in the Subtle World subtle world we see that it is the sea, and even further in the fiery-spiritual world, it is a kind of mysterious inexpressible sky.

I noticed how quickly time has passed and there are only six minutes left to come to conclusions, analyze the last picture, and finish. I really enjoyed how Nida stated earlier in her post that this meeting is like an academic workshop where we learn and look for ways to access Čiurlionis, and how to share our research and feelings. Saloméja's idea was very helpful in reviving us and allowing us to feel and feel more. Going back to the main idea of my presentation mentioned at the beginning, I believe it is very important to learn to pay attention to what is called ineffable, in other words what is not. And here the concept of Chinese *Dao* provides interesting associations, and this idea of *qi* can be especially helpful. Because according to the idea of *qi*, a picture has *qi*, and what we see is just a gate, behind which lies a world of *qi* energy. This energy can spread on its own, again in Saloméja's words, we are looking for ways to allow it to unfold and speak for itself.

More briefly on the last picture, I will say that the towers symbolize a great human achievement, pointing upwards in direction. And these flags, as Nida has already mentioned, are very reminiscent of liberated happy souls leaving this world, and also traveling in this S or Z-shaped trajectory. Even further there we see, as it were, a man showing the way, leading souls – as a deity, a force of nature, a guiding force. And again, the direction here is to the ineffable, to what is not, to infinity, which lies beyond the picture and which Čiurlionis teaches us to see. As Naglis Kardelis said in his message, “See what is beyond” or what is not in the picture.

So, what Čiurlionis portrays can be accepted as faraway worlds, faraway but very important to us here. Faraway, but at the same time real and very real. Perhaps that other world that we all eventually go to and stay there for a long time is much more real than what we see in this everyday physical reality. According to *Dao*, Čiurlionis masterfully embodies the idea of *Dao-Path*, because *Dao* is always something more, something we strive to as a source of light. With each growth of consciousness, this *Dao* as some invisible light, takes a step further away, but keeps calling and guiding us.

Perhaps in conclusion, I want to point out that if we understand *Dao* as light, as bright *qi-energy*, it is very interesting to look at it longer, each painting creating a sense it has at least one or more light sources coming from beyond.

In the painting *Allegro*, the light seems to emanate from beyond the painting, from somewhere far away, from infinity, and we can see it here as well. In the windmill painting, due to the realization that there is another invisible windmill above, somewhere beyond, that windmill also becomes a source of light or sun. I would say there is a light source that comes from here. A similar theme is repeated in the painting of the fish, but what is still interesting here is the impression that there is yet another inner deep light that comes from depths below and illuminates the large fish in a golden color. There is also a theme of hidden suns here, which seem to be hiding their light behind the hills, or even in the mountains.

Finally, as Naglis Kardelis aptly observed earlier, here we have a view from great heights, great distances, and light is emanating from somewhere far away and illuminating everything. When empathized with the concept of *qi* or energy, light is also energy. An energy that moves and travels, and whose movement we can feel, but find it very difficult to put into words.

It was my attempt using clumsy and not always appropriate words to try to touch what is ineffable, the realm that belongs not to words, but to the inner-spiritual world. I hope that at least one idea or another, or an image has evoked in the listeners associations and thoughts that have proven useful. And I hope that we will continue to develop this discussion by sharing information about Čiurlionis, Čiurlionis' paintings, and become more and more empathetic by finding new depths and meanings. Thank you for listening.

Julius Vaitkevičius

NEIŠREIŠKIAMAS ČIURLIONIO DAO-KELIAS: TOLIMŲ PASAULIŲ
ATSPINDŽIAI „SONATINĖS TAPYBOS“ KŪRINIUOSE

Santrauka

Straipsnyje nagrinėjamos 氣 Qi ir 道 Dao sąvokos, kurios padeda naujai pažvelgti į M. K. Čiurlionio tapybą. Tokia prieiga padeda ne tik iš naujo atrasti Čiurlionį, sykiu ir Čiurlionio kūryba padeda geriau suprasti ir paaiškinti šias iš pažiūros abstrakčias sąvokas. Qi ir Dao sąvokos yra neatsiejamos nuo kinų estetikos. Jų abiejų neišsemiamumas atskleidžia dimensiją, kuri pažadina žiūrovą gyvam judėjimui, išlaisvina iš „miegančių“ objektų pasaulio ribotumo. Qi ir Dao sąvokos leidžia kalbėti apie Čiurlionio tapybą pasitelkiant Vakarų estetikoje dar neišplėtotas įžvalgas. Tad straipsnyje plėtojama tarpkultūrinio dialogo dimensija atveria naujus kelius ir į komparatyvistinę estetiką.

Raktažodžiai: M. K. Čiurlionis, 氣 qi, 道 Dao, komparatyvistinė estetika, kultūrų dialogas, neišreiškiamumas, būtis ir nebūtis.